

An approach to predict fatigue delamination propagation in curved composite laminates under non-constant mixed-mode conditions: experiments and simulation correlation

EASN International Conference on

Innovation in aviation & Space towards sustainability today and tomorrow

Session title: Simulation and experimental validation of sustainable aircraft structures and their manufacturing processes

14-17/10/2025, Madrid (Spain), Carlos Mallor (ITA)

1 Introduction

Predicting fatigue-driven delamination in curved composite laminates under non-constant mixed-mode conditions using a VCCT-based approach

Background: Delamination in Composite Materials

- Material and structural discontinuities → interlaminar stresses
- Delaminations pose a complex problem
- Difficult to model and predict
- Demo case: Spar
- Primary structure component ensuring structural integrity and damage tolerance

AERnnova

Sources of delaminations at geometric and material discontinuities

Front Spar of the torsion box of a horizontal stabilizer of an Aircraft

2 Methodology

Predicting fatigue-driven delamination in curved composite laminates under non-constant mixed-mode conditions using a VCCT-based approach

Fatigue Delamination Growth (FDG) methodology: Static & Fatigue

- Delamination = propagation of existing delamination cracks
- Modelling: Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM)

Static case

Finite Element Method (FEM)

+ Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) to compute (G)

$$\phi = (G_{II} + G_{III}) / G_T$$

$$G_T = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}$$

+ BK model

Fatigue case

+ Paris Law & Model for non-constant mixed-mode

UMIX MODE FATIGUE

Paris' law fatigue delamination growth rate

Paris' law variants: $f(G)$ in composites can be based on: ΔG as the arithmetic difference

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \cdot (G_{max} - G_{min})^n$$

DCB Mode I ($\phi = 0$) Fatigue

Delamination growth rate, da/dN [mm/cycle] – ΔG [N/mm]

For ΔG arithmetic-based: $C = 615.3$, $n = 9.030$

Non-constant mixed-mode

ENF Mode II ($\phi = 1$) Fatigue

Delamination growth rate, da/dN [mm/cycle] – ΔG [N/mm]

For ΔG arithmetic-based: $C = 0.003$, $n = 4.0$

Fatigue delamination under non-constant mixed-mode

Non-monotonic model with respect to the mode mix [blanco et al. 2004](#)

The fatigue delamination growth rate da/dN can be generalised to account for the mode mix

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \boxed{C} \cdot (G_{max} - G_{min})^{\boxed{n}}$$

Interpolate material data C and n for the local mode-mixity and load ratio $f(\phi, R)$

Two parabolic equations are suggested to model the material parameters C and n .

$$\log C = c_1 + c_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + c_3 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$

$$n = n_1 + n_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + n_3 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$

Considering pure mode I, $c_1 = \log C_I$ and $n_1 = n_I$. Including the mode II and mixed-mode parameters, the equations become:

$$\log C = \log C_I + \log C_m \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + \log \frac{C_{II}}{C_I C_m} \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$

$$n = n_I + n_m \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + (n_{II} - n_I - n_m) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$

where C_m and n_m are the extra mixed-mode parameters that must be determined by curve fitting (experimentally derived factors).

Adapted from:
[vallejo et al. 2019](#)

3 Results and Discussion

Predicting fatigue-driven delamination in curved composite laminates under non-constant mixed-mode conditions using a VCCT-based approach

Exp. test configuration: 4-point bending (4PB) Mixed-mode on L-angle specimen.

Delamination under **Unfolding conditions** (curvature of the spar)

IMA21E TAPE (epoxy resin matrix M21E/IMA-12K carbon fibres) **AIRBUS A350**

Stacking UD20: $[0]_{20} = [(0)_{10} / T / (0)_{10}]$

Delamination length $a_0=15\text{mm}$ off-centred

Fatigue loading: Applied fatigue displacement $\delta=1\text{ mm}$

Displ controlled

Exp. test configuration: 4PB Mixed-mode on L-angle specimen, Fatigue

No standard for fatigue crack propagation in CFRP → follow the standard for metals ASTM E647-24, 2024

ASTM E647 - 24. Standard Test Method for Measurement of Fatigue Crack Growth Rates

4PB mixed mode test rig configuration for fatigue testing

DIC for delamination length

FE-model results: 4PB Mixed-mode on L-angle specimen, Fatigue

Fatigue delamination under non-constant mixed-mode: FEM + VCCT to compute (G) & UMIXMODE FATIGUE

3D Model: continuum solid elements (C3D8I)

Delamination propagation under fatigue (rendering undeformed shape)

Detail of delamination initiation

N=490 cycles, a = 0.5 mm

Detail of delamination growth

N=22511 cycles, a = 4 mm

Detail of delamination growth

N=108731 cycles, a = 6 mm

Detail of final front shape

N=300000 cycles, a = 8 mm

FE-model results: 4PB Mixed-mode on L-angle specimen, Fatigue

Fatigue delamination under non-constant mixed-mode: FEM + VCCT to compute (G) & UMIXMODE FATIGUE

Displ. controlled: Applied displacement $\delta = 1$ mm

Force max & min, P [N] – Applied cycles, N [Cycles]

Crack length a [mm] – N [Cycles]

Energy Release rate, G_{max} [N/mm] – N [Cycles]

Energy Release rate, G_{max} [N/mm] – a [mm]

Objective: Validation. Good correlation between numerical prediction and the experimental measurements.

Non-monotonic model with respect to the mode mix

4 Conclusions

Predicting fatigue-driven delamination in curved composite laminates under non-constant mixed-mode conditions using a VCCT-based approach

Conclusions

- Experimental tests on M21E/IMA-12K material:

- Mode-I DCB and Mode-II ENF **static** and **fatigue tests** were performed.
- **Non-constant mixed-mode 4PB** on **L-angle specimen** **static** and **fatigue tests** were done.

- Numerical simulations analysis: L-angle specimen **static** and **fatigue**:

- The approach was developed for ABAQUS (VCCT) + U MIXMODE FATIGUE for **2D** and **3D**.
- A model for **non-constant mixed-mode** enables modelling the experimental fatigue behaviour **observed**.

- Systematic correlation of model predictions with experimental data:

- Results from FEM growth analyses were in good agreement both in **static** and **fatigue**.
- The methodology developed accurately predicts **FDG** under **varying mode mixity**.

Enhanced fatigue delamination modelling will be applied in the spar demonstration case, enabling timely maintenance and helping to prevent fatigue failures.

THANK YOU!

“ When the physical world meets, uniquely, the virtual world for a premium manufacturing, maintenance, and repair approach of the next generation aircraft composite structures ”

cmallor@ita.es

<https://www.ita.es>

<https://www.genex-project.eu>

C/ María de Luna, nº7-8 (Pol. Actur) · 50018 Zaragoza Spain

Funded by
the European Union